

New protolimonoids and limonoids. Part-IV. Transformation of naturally occurring 6 α -acetoxyazadirone to new limonoids

N. K. Bhattacharyya, G. K. Sarmah, B. N. Goswami, N. Borthakur and J. C. S. Katakya*

Organic Chemistry Division, Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat-785 006, India

E-mail : katakycjs@sancharnet.in

Fax : 91-376-2370011

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Paniculation (1) (6 α -acetoxyazadirone), a naturally occurring meliacin, has been isolated from the fruits of *Chisocheton paniculatus* Hiern. Chemical transformations on paniculatin have been performed to give 1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin (2), 6 α ,7 α -dihydroxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin (3), isopropylidene derivative of 3 (4), 6 α ,7 α -dihydroxypaniculatin (5), isopropylidene derivative of 5 (6).

*Chisocheton paniculatus*¹ Hiern (Family : Meliaceae) occurs as a tree in the forests of Assam, the fruit of which is capsule, 1.5–3 inches across, globose with pyriform base. It has been reported that a number of species of this family exhibit physiological activity².

In our continuing studies³ on the Meliaceae of the NER of India, we have investigated the fruits of *C. paniculatus*, a member of the Meliaceae from this region. The plant material was collected from tropical evergreen forest of Nambor Reserved Forest of Golaghat district of Assam, India during May 2000.

Limonoids have attracted much attention because of the marked insect antifeedant and growth regulating, antifungal activity of azadirachtin and related limonoids isolated from the neem tree and also of few limonoids isolated from the fruits of *C. paniculatus* Hiern⁴⁻⁶. More recently limonoids have shown anticarcinogenic and antitumour activities⁶. We report here the isolation, identification of known paniculatin (1), and its chemical transformation.

Petroleum ether extract of powdered fruit yielded a complex mixture of several compounds. After careful chromatographic separation one compound was isolated and on crystallization from benzene : MeOH (9 : 1) gave pure crystalline white plates, m.p. 192°. The compound gave purple spot on TLC plate when sprayed with vanillin/H₂SO₄ followed by heating at 100°. A positive Libermann-Burchard reaction and a yellow coloration with tetranitromethane (TNM) indicated that the compound is an unsaturated triterpene. The pure compound was identified as paniculatin (1) by a comparison of its m.p., IR and ¹H NMR data with the reported values³, as well as

by comparing with authentic samples.

Mild alkaline hydrolysis of 1 with methanolic KOH gave the corresponding diol 5, C₂₆H₃₄O₄, m.p. 181°. In the ¹H NMR spectrum of 5 the 2 protons geminal to the acetoxy groups appearing at δ 5.42 and 5.47 in 1 shifted and appeared as multiplet centered at δ 4.30.

Treatment of the diol 5 with acetone in the presence of catalytic amount of sulfuric acid at RT gave the corresponding isopropylidene derivative (6), C₂₉H₃₈O₄, m.p. 68°, indicating that the two hydroxyl groups in the diol 5 were *cis* to each other.

Hydrogenation of paniculatin (**1**) in presence of palladium/calcium carbonate gave the product **2**, characterized as 1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin, $C_{30}H_{44}O_6$, m.p. 213°. In the 1H NMR spectrum, the appearance of new signals at δ 2.06, 2.61, 2.80, 4.14, 4.18 and disappearance of olefinic and furanoid proton signals at δ 6.39, 6.62, 6.80 and 7.53 suggest hydrogenation at these carbons.

Mild alkaline hydrolysis of **2** with methanolic KOH gave the corresponding diol **3**, characterized as 6 α ,7 α -dihydroxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin, $C_{26}H_{40}O_4$, m.p. 95°. The disappearance of acetate peaks in the 1H NMR spectrum confirms the formation of the diol **3**. Treatment of **3** with acetone in presence of catalytic amount of sulfuric acid at RT as in the case of diol **5** gave the corresponding isopropylidene derivative (**4**), $C_{29}H_{44}O_4$, m.p. 65°.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries on a Mettler FP 62 apparatus and are uncorrected. Optical rotations were taken on a AA1000 polarimeter. UV spectra (MeOH) were recorded on Hitachi 320 and Jasco UV-Vis 7800 spectrophotometers, IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 2000 FT-IR spectrophotometer, 1H NMR spectra on a Varian EM-360 L spectrometer using TMS as internal reference and mass spectra on a LC-MS, Bruker esquire 3000 spectrometer. TLC and preparative-TLC were performed on silica gel G (Merck) and column chromatography on silica gel (B.D.H.) of 60–120 mesh size.

The fruits of *C. paniculatus* Hiern. were collected from Nambor Reserved Forest of Golaghat, Assam, India during May 2000. Identification was made by Dr. S. C. Nath, Scientist, Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat from the Herbarium species maintained in the Institute.

Collected fruits of *C. paniculatus* were shed-dried and ground. The powdered fruits (500 g) was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) in a soxhlet apparatus. The extract on concentration under reduced pressure gave a light yellow material (15 g) which was washed with petroleum ether followed by ethanol.

Paniculatin (**1**), the reported limonoid was isolated from the oil obtained after trituration of the gummy material with pet. ether, as a pure compound (CC, TLC, PTLC) and identified by comparing with an authentic sample (TLC, IR, m.m.p.).

Paniculatin (**1**): Crystalline solid (MeOH), m.p. 192° (lit.³, 186–188°); $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ 118° (c 0.5) (lit.³ 119°) (c 0.5); λ_{max} 220 nm (ϵ 10000); ν_{max} 1750, 1675, 1505 and 875 cm^{-1} ; EIMS (70 eV) m/z [M^+] 494; calcd. 494.6266 for $C_{30}H_{38}O_6$.

Compound 2: 6 α -Acetoxiazadirone (**1**) (paniculatin) (1 g, 2.0 mmol) in methanol (40 ml) was stirred with palladium/calcium carbonate (0.5 g) under an atmosphere of H_2 for 6 h in a PAR hydrogenation apparatus. The mixture was filtered. Removal of solvent under reduced pressure gave 1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin (**2**), which was crystallized from methanol, m.p. 213°. The spectral data are given in the Table 1.

Table 1. Physical and spectral data of compounds 1-6

Compd.	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Molecular weight (g)	Molecular formula	IR (ν_{max} cm^{-1})	1H NMR (δ ppm)
1	192	3	494	$C_{30}H_{38}O_6$	1750 (C=O), 1675 (C=O), 1505, 875 (β -substituted furan)	1.13 (s, 5- CH_3), 2.16 (6H, s, 2-Ac), 6.39 (1H, d, H-1), 6.80 (1H, d, H-2), 5.42 (1H, H-6), 5.47 (1H, H-7), 7.51 and 7.53 (1H, m, furan α -H), 6.62 (1H, m, furan β -H)
2	213	98	500	$C_{30}H_{44}O_6$	1737 (C=O), 1645 (C=O)	1.13 and 0.87 (s, 5- CH_3), 2.06 (1H, d, H-1), 2.80 (1H, d, H-2), 2.61 (s, H-20), 2.06 (s, H-22), 4.18 (s, H-21), 4.14 (s, H-23)
3	95	97	416	$C_{26}H_{40}O_4$	1700 (C=O), 3458 (OH)	2.06 (1H, d, H-1), 2.80 (1H, d, H-2), 2.61 (s, H-20), 2.06 (s, H-22), 4.18 (s, H-21), 4.14 (s, H-23), 3.70 (2H, s, OH)
4	65	80	456	$C_{29}H_{44}O_4$	1670 (C=O)	2.06 (1H, d, H-1), 2.80 (1H, d, H-2), 3.37 (6H, s, acetonide)
5	181	94	410	$C_{26}H_{34}O_4$	3443 (OH), 1662 (C=O), 1501 and 873 (β -substituted furan)	3.90 (H, s, OH), 4.30 (2H, m, H-6,7)
6	68	85	450	$C_{29}H_{38}O_4$	1670 (C=O), 1512 and 875 (β -substituted furan)	3.37 (6H, s, acetonide)

Note

Compound 3 : 1,2,20,21,22,23-Hexahydropaniculatin (**2**) (0.5 g, 1.01 mmol) was set aside at RT for 12 h in methanolic KOH (5%; 25 ml) and then refluxed for 2 h in a boiling water-bath. The usual work up gave the corresponding diol 6 α ,7 α -dihydroxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin (**3**), which was crystallized from methanol, m.p. 95°.

Compound 4 : The diol (**3**; 0.1 g, 0.24 mmol) was kept at RT in dry acetone (20 ml) with two drops of conc. H₂SO₄. The mixture was stirred and monitored the progress by TLC. The reaction was completed within 2 h. The excess acetone was then removed under reduced pressure. The residue was diluted with water and the product extracted with ether. Removal of ether under reduced pressure gave the required isopropylidene derivative (**4**), which was crystallized from methanol, m.p. 65°.

Compound 5 : Paniculatin (**1**; 0.5 g, 1.01 mmol) was set aside at RT for 12 h in methanolic KOH (5%; 25 ml) and then refluxed for 2 h in a water-bath. The usual work up gave the corresponding diol **5** which was crystallized from methanol, m.p. 181°.

Compound 6 : Taking the diol **5** (0.1 g, 0.24 mmol), compound **6** was prepared following the same procedure

as described for compound **4**, m.p. 68°.

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